

CR289-1008 and CR289-1208—very early-maturingrices

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Rice varieties with 10- to 12-week crop cycles are grown in India in rainfed dryland conditions during monsoon season. They yield low and do not perform well in intensive cropping systems.

CR289-1008 and CR289-1208 are shortduration varieties evolved from the cross ARC12422/ARC12751 through hybridization. They mature at 75 and 80 days, respectively, and yield 2.4 to 3.5 t/ha (see table).

CR289-1008 has medium stature, produces long slender grains, and lodges partially at maturity. CR289-1208 is a

Performance of CR289-1008 and CR289-1208 in wet and dry season, Cuttack, India.

Variety	Plant ht (cm)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha) ^a		
			1980 wet season	1981 dry season	1982 dry season
CR289-1008	108	75	2.8	2.4	3.1
CR289-1208	77	80	3.3	2.7	3.5

^aSeeded on 5 July 1980, 1 March 1981, and 1 February 1982.

semidwarf variety that produces coarse grains with golden-brown hulls. It does not lodge. Both varieties are photoperiod insensitive and perform well in rainfed dryland and irrigated conditions.

The short crop cycle of CR289-1008 and CR289-1208 requires specific crop management. Because the vegetative phase is short, tillering time is limited. Proper seed rate is necessary to maintain optimum density of ear-bearing tillers, and direct seeding in dry or puddled soil

may be needed to ensure ample vegetative growth and full panicle size. The initial vegetative stage of the crop also needs special weed control and fertilizer management efforts because vegetative growth overlaps panicle development.

Very short-maturity varieties such as CR289-1008 and CR289-1208 might help produce four crops a year in an intensive rice-based cropping system if suitable infrastructure is available. ✎

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

KMP-1 (Mandya Vani)—a new short duration, high yielding, superfine paddy released in Karnataka, India

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KMP-1 is a new rice variety released in Karnataka, India, in 1982. It is a cryptic genetic variant isolated from the cross CR1014/IR8. It matures in 120-125 days and yields 5.5-6.5 t rough rice/ha. In 16 varietal experiments from 1979 to 1980, KMP-1 gave an average yield of 5.5 t/ha (Table 1). In rice minikit trials during 1980-82 KMP-1 produced 22.9% higher yield than Telhamsa and 8.36%

more than Pushpa Paddy. KMP-1 is blast tolerant, has limited grain shattering, and long panicles with superfine spikelets, and cooks flaky with good volume expansion.

KMP-1 milling properties and cooking quality compare favorably with

those of well-known varieties Sona, IR20, Basmati 370, J192, and Mahsuri. KMP-1 length-breadth ratio is 3.7, compared with 3.6 for Sona. Hulling and milling qualities are equal to those of IR20, but KMP-1 recorded 2.6% less head rice than IR20.

Table 1. Grain yield (av of 1979-81) for KMP-1 and check varieties, Karnataka, India.

Trials (no.)	Check variety	Yield (t/ha)		Check (%)
		KMP-1	Check	
5	Jaya	5.1	5.5	93.1
3	Rasi	5.0	4.8	104.6
1	Prakash	5.6	6.7	82.7
3	Mangala	4.9	4.6	106.7
1	Ratna	5.7	5.5	103.5
2	IR20	6.6	6.4	102.5
Average		5.5		

Table 2. Chemical properties and cooking quality of KMP-1 and selected varieties, Karnataka, India.

Variety	Abdominal white ^a	Kernel elongation	Volume expansion	Alkali value	Amylose (%)	Protein (%)	cooking quality
Sona	Wb	1.7	4.0	6.7	23.6	8.7	Good
KMP-1	Abs	1.8	4.9	4.5	26.7	8.4	Excellent
IR20	Abs	1.6	4.2	4.5	24.3	8.3	Excellent
Basmati 370	Abs	2.0	4.2	4.5	23.9	7.8	Excellent
Mahsuri	Abs	1.9	3.8	4.5	26.4	7.6	Excellent
J-192	Abs	1.6	4.1	4.5	24.6	—	Excellent
Experimental mean (X)		1.7	4.1	4.7	23.7	7.8	—
Sem (+)		0.02	0.09	0.16	0.28	0.09	—

^aWb= white belly, Abs = absent.

KMP-1 kernel elongation ratio is 1.8, compared with 1.7 for Sona and 2.0 for Basmati 370. It recorded a volume expansion ratio of 4.9, compared with

4.2 of IR20 and 4.1 of J-192. Alkali value and amylose content equal those of IR20 (Table 2).

KMP-1 is gaining popularity, especially in the traditionally fine-grain rice growing districts of Karnataka. ✎

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Reaction of tall and dwarf rice varieties to bacterial leaf blight

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A collection of 104 rice varieties, 74 dwarf and 30 tall, were evaluated for reaction to bacterial leaf blight *Xanthomonas oryzae* (BLB) during 1981-82 kharif at the Pattambi RRS.

Varieties were dry seeded in dryland nursery beds, then irrigated and maintained under wet conditions. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha. At panicle initiation, plants were clip inoculated with BLB suspension. Disease incidence was recorded 15 days after 50% flowering, using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

No entry was free of infection, 33 showed resistant to moderately resistant reactions, 58 moderately susceptible to susceptible, and 13 highly susceptible (see table). Of the tall varieties tested, 50% were susceptible or highly susceptible; 65% of these were local varieties. ✎

Reaction^a of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial leaf blight. 1981-82 kharif, Pattambi Rice Research Station, Kerala, India.

Resistance rating	Dwarf varieties	Tall varieties
R	IR8-68, IR5, Jayanthi, Bhadra, Jagannath, Sakthi	H4, Pokkali, Malinga, Mashoory, Bluebonnet, Mala, Bhavani
MR	IR8, IR20, IR22, IR26, IR42, Cul. 4, Cul. 23178, Cul. 23332-2, Cul. 23372, BR51, Hema, Pankaj, Annapoorna, Rasi, Jamuna, Suma, Pennai, Suphala	Kolappala, Vyttila I
MS	IR28, IR30, IR32, IR34, PR106, Cul. 1-5-4, Cul. 1999, Au-1, Jaya, Sona, Vijaya, Vani, Rohini, Jyothy, Karuma, Cauveri, Madhu, Hamsa, Supriya, Kumar, Parijath, Rajendra, Kalinga I	H105, Basmathi, Ptb 1, Ptb 2, Ptb 5, Vyttila-11
S	IR36, Cul. 3, Cul. 1180, Cul. 12035, Cul. 12814, Cul. 1065, Cul. 7944, MN54-42, Aswathy, Sabary, Satya, Soorya, Suhasini, Rajeswari, DGWG, Triveni, Bala, Krishna, Ratna, Anupama, Kannagi, Kalinga 11	Purple, Chennellu, Ptb 8, Ptb 9, Ptb 22, Ptb 28, Ptb 32
HS	IR1552, T(N) 1, Bharathy, Kanchi, Padma	Suvarna modan, Cul. 25064, Cul. 1907, Ptb 10, Ptb 26, Ptb 29, Ptb 30

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Sesamia inferens — a serious pest of rice in Uttar Pradesh Hills, India

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Stem borer epidemics in pockets of the Uttar Pradesh Hills occur regularly in irrigated valleys and in direct-seeded dryland rice. In a survey of the Kumaon hills and of experimental fields of

VLHA, 50-60% infestations were recorded.

The pest has been identified as *Sesamia inferens* Wlk (pink stem borer). In other parts of India, *Tryporyza incertulas* Wlk (yellow stem borer) has been reported a major problem. Pink stem borers also attack several other crops grown in this region: ragi (*Eleusine coracana*), Japanese barnyard millet (*Echinochloa frumentacea*), and maize (*Zea mays*).

Low infestation on rice occurs in early July, when larvae cause deadhearts in seedlings. Severe infestations occur in September, with maximum whiteheads in late September.

To identify sources of pink borer resistance, a large number of genotypes were screened. Some promising entries that showed low infestation were also screened under partially artificial conditions. IR8866-30-3, IR9202-56-1, and IR5908-21-2-1 showed high resistance.

In experiments on chemical control, sprays of chlorpyrifos 20 EC, monocrotophos, and carbaryl 50 WP were effective. ✎